

IMAGE BASED PRODUCT RECOMMENDATION USING CNN

Chithira C B
Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering
Kanjirapally,India
chithiracb2024a@mca.ajce.in

Ms.Sona Maria Sebastian
Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering
Kanjirapally,India
sonasebastian@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Image-based product recommendation systems using deep learning and transfer learning techniques have been a focal point in recent research. While traditional recommendation systems are effective, they often grapple with issues like data sparsity and scalability. This study introduces an innovative approach that harnesses pre-trained Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to extract key features from product images, capturing their essential visual attributes. As a result, the system can suggest visually similar products to the user's query image, facilitating personalized recommendations based on visual appeal. The effectiveness of this method is demonstrated through its ability to generate relevant product suggestions. However, the study acknowledges potential biases from pre-trained models and scalability challenges as areas needing further exploration. To address these concerns, future enhancements are proposed, including incorporating user preferences and exploring advanced deep learning models to improve the accuracy and scalability of image-based product recommendation systems.

Keywords— Image-based Recommendation, Deep Learning, Transfer Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Product Recommendation Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the global markets that is expanding the fastest is e-commerce websites. All individuals desire to utilize the internet to place product orders. It's critical that e-commerce websites offer the greatest user experience to entice people to make purchases on their websites. Offering a customized recommendation system to every customer is one of the main actions that e-commerce websites have taken to enhance the user experience.

Recommendation systems are fundamental tools in modern information technology and e-commerce. They serve the critical role of suggesting items or content to users based on their preferences, behaviors, and historical interactions. By leveraging various algorithms and data analytics techniques, recommendation systems enhance user experience by providing personalized and relevant suggestions, thereby increasing engagement, customer satisfaction, and ultimately driving sales.

The core idea behind image-based recommendations using ResNet is to derive detailed representations from images using the ResNet model. These representations are then leveraged to generate personalized suggestions. Contrasted with traditional recommendation systems relying on user-item interactions or content-based filtering, this method offers several advantages. Image-based recommendations can offer more accurate and varied suggestions by utilizing visual information that might not be discernible through textual attributes alone. Additionally, ResNet acts as an efficient feature extractor, adept at capturing both user preferences and item attributes effectively.

This approach has the potential to create sophisticated visual displays, enhancing user experience by offering a visually appealing interface and facilitating the discovery of new products through visual exploration. As a result, implementing image-based recommendations has been shown to elevate the overall user experience.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

D.N.V.S.L.S. Indira, Babu Rao Markapudi, Kavitha Chaduvula, Rathna Jyothi Chaduvula[1] in their paper titled "Visual and buying sequence features-based product image recommendation using optimization-based deep residual network," introduced innovative techniques for enhancing recommendation systems in e-commerce. Their approach leverages deep residual networks and Elephant Herding Feedback Artificial Optimization (EHFAO) for improved product recommendations based on image data. The integration of K-means clustering, cosine similarity matching, and sentiment analysis further refines the recommendation process, leading to superior performance metrics compared to traditional methods. This research contributes valuable insights into advanced recommendation system methodologies, emphasizing the importance of personalized recommendations and enhanced user experiences in e-commerce platforms.

Pegah Malekpour Alamdari, Nima Jafari Navimipour, Mehdi Hosseinzadeh, Ali Asghar Safaei , Aso Darwesh[2] in their paper titled "Image-based Product Recommendation Method

for E-commerce Applications Using Convolutional Neural Networks” presents an image-based recommender system using five CNN models for feature extraction from product images and evaluates its accuracy with various MovieLens datasets. Significant accuracy improvements over traditional methods were observed. The study also identifies future research directions, including the use of multiple images per item, different similarity metrics, additional CNN models, and hybridization with other recommender system techniques, offering promising avenues for enhancing e-commerce product recommendations.

Ping Lu, Pingping Liu[3] in their paper titled “Product Recommendation System Based on Deep Learning” explores personalized recommendation systems, emphasizing the importance of accurate content delivery based on user preferences across diverse scenarios. It employs a classic DNN double tower recommendation algorithm using TensorFlow for model construction and feature engineering techniques like tfidf and w2v for system accuracy and balance. The recommendation module includes user profiling, multiple recall algorithms, and deep learning, aiming for a balanced platform-user relationship and mutual benefit.

Biresh Kumar, Ayush Kumar Singh, Pallab Banerjee[4] in their paper “A Deep Learning Approach for Product Recommendation using ResNet-50 CNN Model” explores image-based product recommendation systems using deep learning and transfer learning, particularly Reverse Image Search. It discusses utilizing the ResNet-50 CNN model for feature extraction and proposes improvements to address challenges like bias and scalability, emphasizing the need for enhanced accuracy and user preference incorporation.

Luyang Chen, Fan Yang, Heqing Yang[5] in their paper “Image-based Product Recommendation System with Convolutional Neural Networks” addresses the challenge of information overload in online shopping by proposing a smart recommendation system based on image classification and similarity scoring using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). It aims to improve the online shopping experience by allowing users to search and receive recommendations based on images instead of text descriptions, enhancing efficiency and accuracy.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection:

In this step, you gather comprehensive information about the products you want to recommend on your e-commerce platform. This includes collecting product images, product names, descriptions, and any other relevant metadata.

B. Preprocessing:

Before inputting the images into the ResNet50 model, preprocessing steps are essential. The images are resized to a

standardized size of 224x224 pixels. This step ensures that all images are in the same format, which is crucial for consistency during feature extraction. Additionally, the images are converted into arrays, a format suitable for machine learning algorithms. Pixel values in the images are normalized to a specific range, typically between 0 and 1, to ensure numerical stability during processing.

C. Feature Extraction:

ResNet50 is a deep neural network architecture that has been pre-trained on a vast dataset of images from the ImageNet dataset. By utilizing ResNet50, extract high-level features from product images. These features represent significant characteristics of the images, such as shapes, textures, and patterns, learned during the model's training on ImageNet.

D. Building Product Feature Database:

Once features are extracted from all product images using ResNet50, create a database of product features. This database pairs each product's extracted features with its corresponding image filenames. The product feature database serves as a repository of essential information that will be used during the recommendation process.

E. Querying Product Feature Database:

When a user uploads an image to the system, the uploaded image undergoes the same preprocessing steps as the product images. The ResNet50 model is then used to extract features from the user-uploaded image. These features capture the visual characteristics of the uploaded image.

F. Product Recommendation:

Using the k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm, the system queries the product feature database to find the k most similar products to the user-uploaded image based on their feature similarities. The k most similar products are then presented to the user as personalized product recommendations. These recommendations are based on the visual similarities between the user's uploaded image and the product images in the database.

```
uploaded_file = st.file_uploader("Choose an image")
if uploaded_file is not None:
    if save_uploaded_file(uploaded_file):
        # display the file
        display_image = Image.open(uploaded_file)
        st.image(display_image)
        # feature extract
        features = feature_extraction(os.path.join("uploads", uploaded_file.name), model)
        st.text(features)
        indices = recommend(features, feature_list)

        col1, col2, col3, col4, col5 = st.columns(5)
        # Use the columns to display images
        col1.image(filenamees[indices[0][0]])
        col2.image(filenamees[indices[0][1]])
        col3.image(filenamees[indices[0][2]])
        col4.image(filenamees[indices[0][3]])
        col5.image(filenamees[indices[0][4]])

    else:
        st.header("Some error occurred in file upload")
```

Fig. 1

Fig.1 includes the code for an image upload feature within a Streamlit application, designed for the extraction of features and recommendation of similar product images. Upon successful image upload, the system initiates a file saving check, ensuring data integrity. If successful, the uploaded image is visually displayed using Streamlit's UI components. Simultaneously, features are extracted from the image utilizing the ResNet50 deep learning model, a pivotal step for subsequent recommendation tasks.

IV. RESULT

Fig. 2 depicts the search done by uploading image from user end. Users can upload an image of a product, and the system processes the uploaded image using a pre-trained CNN model. This model extracts intricate features from the image, enabling the system to identify similar products from the dataset.

Fig. 2

The system displays the top recommendations that closely match the uploaded image, as illustrated in Fig 3.

Fig 3

Overall, the system leverages CNNs to deliver accurate, relevant, and recommendations, thereby enhancing user satisfaction and engagement in online shopping scenarios.

V. CONCLUSION

The research presents an innovative image-based product recommendation system leveraging Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and k-nearest neighbors algorithms. Through the integration of a pre-trained ResNet50 model for feature extraction and Streamlit for interactive web application development, demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of personalized product recommendations based on user-uploaded images. The system's ability to accurately identify visually similar products and provide meaningful recommendations enhances the user experience in e-commerce platforms, ultimately contributing to improved user engagement and satisfaction. Our findings showcase the potential of deep learning techniques in enhancing recommendation systems and pave the way for further advancements in personalized user experiences in online shopping environments.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] D. N. V. S. L. S. Indira, B. R. Markapudi, K. Chaduvula, and R. J. Chaduvula, (2022), "Product Recommendation System Based on Deep Learning", *Gene Expression Patterns*, Vol. 45, pp. 1-14.
- [2] P. M. Alamdari, N. J. Navimipour, M. Hosseinzadeh, A. A. Safaei, and A. Darwesh, (2022), "Image-based Product Recommendation Method for E-commerce Applications Using Convolutional Neural Networks", *Acta Informatica Pragensia*, Vol. 11, pp. 15-35.
- [3] P. Lu and P. Liu, (2023), "Product Recommendation System Based on Deep Learning", *International Journal of Advanced Network, Monitoring and Controls*, Vol. 08, pp.1-9.
- [4] B. Kumar, A. K. Singh, and P. Banerjee, (2023), "A Deep Learning Approach for Product Recommendation using ResNet-50 CNN Model," in *Proceedings of the 2023 International Conference on Sustainable Computing and Smart Systems (ICSCSS)*.
- [5] L. Chen, F. Yang, and H. Yang, (2020), "Image-based Product Recommendation System with Convolutional Neural Networks," in *Special Section on Gigapixel Panoramic Video with Virtual Reality*,
- [6] G. Zhang, J. Zhang, Z. Zhang, and Y. Gu, (2021), "Visual Search and Recommendation System using Deep Learning and Graph-based Algorithm", in *Proceedings of the 2021 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Computer Applications*, pp. 1-6.
- [7] S. Vijayakumar, K. Raja, and S. Sathiy, "A Deep Learning-Based Product Recommendation System using ResNet50 and Convolutional Neural Network", (2021), in *Proceedings of the 2021 International Conference on Emerging Trends in Communication, Control, Signal Processing and Computing Applications*, pp. 253-259.
- [8] M. V. K. S. K. Mahesh, S. Senthil Kumar, and K. Thangaraj, (2021), "An Image-Based Product Recommendation System using ResNet50 and Collaborative Filtering Algorithm," in *Proceedings of the 2021 International Conference on Data, Engineering and Applications*, pp. 159-164..
- [9] L. Yu, F. Han, S. Huang, and Y. Luo, (2018) "A content-based goods image recommendation system," *Multimedia Tools Appl.*, Vol. 77, no. 4, pp. 4155-4169.
- [10] S. Bell and K. Bala, (2015), "Learning visual similarity for product design with convolutional neural networks," *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 34, no. 4, p. 98.

- [11] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton, (2012) , “ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks” in Proceedings of. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.,[33] J. Huang, S. R. Kum.
- [12] L. Liu, (2015), “Contextual topic model based image recommendation system”, in Proc. IEEE/WIC/ACM Int. Jt. Conf. Web Intell. Intell. Agent Technol. (WI-IAT), pp. 239–240.